

A STUDY ON STUDENT PERCEPTION TOWARDS BUS FACILITIES IN DHANALAKSHMI SRINIVASAN ENGINEERING COLLEGE (AUTONOMOUS), PERAMBALUR

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Abstract:

The purpose of the project report entitles study on student perception towards transportation facilities in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur. The study is focused on the human resource topic as its valuable resource which is of emotionally controlled and managed in every institution. This project report on study of transport facilities aim sat examining the awareness of the students and also the measures taken by the transport management system. For this study simple random sampling method was used and took 120 samples for the study. There search decision is descriptive in nature and primary data were collected for the responds were recorded. Appropriate tools are used to supplement the analysis and interpretation. Tools like percentage analysis were used. The project report is intended to examine the measures of transport services in the institution and finally to provide suggestions to improve the awareness of day scholar students.

Key Words: Transport Service, Student Satisfaction towards Transport Facilities, Making in and Out Time.

Introduction:

The Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Group of Institutions has more than 250 buses, which are made available to the students and the faculty members from various rural and urban areas. All students should make use of the DS Groups Transporter should stay in the hostel. This facility has made it possible to start the classes in time and thereby helping the academic process. Our bus facilities have enabled us to maintain discipline among students. All though buses reach the Campus before 9.15am, so that all the students and faculty can have their Breakfast and get ready to attend the classes at 9am. The buses leave the campus at 5.00 pm, which helps although students to reach home early and safely. For the benefit of students who are at ending special classes, using internet facility, library etc. special buses are arranged everyday which leaves the campus at 5.30pm.

Available Routes:

- | | | |
|--------------|-----------------|-------------|
| • Ariyalur | • Kunnam | • Sendurai |
| • Arumbavur | • Mannachanalur | • Thirumanu |
| • Attur | • Neyveli | • Thuraiyur |
| • Jayakondam | • Pachaperu | • Trichy |
| • Koppampati | • Samayapuram | • Thitakudi |

Review of Literature:

Partha Chakroborty (2001), discussed unfortunately, it is note as to develop an efficient and sustainable transport system due to the relationship between mobility, land-use, and travel demand, environmental and societal impacts. If we would like to have efficient sustainable transportation infrastructure, infrastructure& urban transportation have to be sustainable in order to integrally connect to a sustainable transportation infrastructure over an extended period of time(farely,2013).

Richard Douthwaite, David Healy and Kevin Leyden A (2003) have stated transport system can bore graded as sustainable only if it is possible to imagine it being continued unchanged for several hundred years because it is not damaging society or the environment and is not dependent on a non-renewable, depleting resource to run(RichardDouthwaite,2006).

Jeon, C M; Amekudzi (2005) said Sustainable transport defines the broad title of transport that is sustainable in the senses of social, environmental and climate impacts , in the universal scope, reserve the source energy unlimited. Factors for apprising sustainability include the private vehicles used for road, transport way such a said and water; energy cause; and the provided infrastructure to embed the different types of transport ways. (CARB,2004).

The University of Plymouth Centre (2009) provided a widely accepted definition of a sustainable transportation system that it allows the basic access need of individuals and societies to be met safely and in a manner consistent with human and ecosystem health, and with equity within and between generations.

The Intelligent Transportation Systems Laboratory at Portland State University produced this guide for students conducting research. The guide includes specific resources available at the university and online, reference styles, notes on plagiarism and copyright, information about presenting research and instructions for writing literature reviews that include examples of good and bad organization.

Objectives of the Study:

- To maintain and improve the accessibility of transport service to students and staffs.
- To analyse the transport service are provided to both rural and urban areas.
- To improve the internal space and sitting arrangements of buses.

Research Methodology:

Research methodology is a systematic process of solving the research problem. It may be understood as role conflict among the students, how research is done scientifically. The method adopted the data, were questionnaire with direct survey.

Research Design:

Study was carried out with the descriptive type of research. Descriptive research is used to describe characteristics of a population or phenomenon being studied.

Sampling Design:

1	Sampling Technique	Simple Random Sampling
2	Sample Size	120
3	Population	1073
4	Sample Area	Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur

Tools for Data Collection:

Primary Data:

The primary data was obtained by questionnaire method.

Statistical Tools Used:

- Percentage Method
- Chi-Square Test
- Correlation
- ANOVA test

Limitations of the Study:

- As opinions are dynamic the Results of the study based on these opinions are likely to differ in future.
- There suit also depends on the Integrity of the respondents in giving true and fair opinions and their level of knowledge in subject understudy.
- The study also in heritsal the limitations of the sampling Technique used for conducting the survey.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Using Transport Facilities are being felt safe:

S.No	Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Strongly Agree	34	28.33
2	Agree	60	50
3	Neutral	16	13.33
4	Strongly Disagree	3	2.50
5	Disagree	7	5.83
	Total	120	100

Source: Primary data

Interpretation:

The above table shows that, 28.33% of students Strongly Agree with the awareness of transport resources, 50% of students agree with the awareness of transport resources, 13.33% of students Neutral with the awareness of transport resources, 2.50% of students Strong Disagree with the awareness of transport resources, 5.83% of students Disagree with the awareness of transport resources.

Chart:

Correlation:

Find it Useful by using transport provided by college (X)	18	69	18	7	8	120
Feel safe While Using Transport (Y)	34	60	16	3	7	120

Answer $r_{xy} = 0.9300$

Inference:

There is high positive correlation between Aware about the transport resource (X) and Satisfied with the resource of transport (Y).

Suggestion:

The researcher has given the following Suggestions to improve the Transportation Facilities of the college.

- In order to maintain and improve the services of transport resources.
- Provide transport services to both rural and urban areas.
- Make sure that transport service helps to maintain the time consuming to reach the college on time.
- Improve the internal space and sitting arrangements are feel comfortable to students.
- A low minimum students to the bus that helps to reduce the crowded.
- Using transport facilities, Parents feel complete peace of mind.

Conclusion:

The study is based on student perception towards transportation facilities in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College. This survey helps to understand and analyse the transportation facilities around our college environment. Therefore the student's gives feedback and suggestion regarding the bus facilities that they can attend the class on time feel safe and secured while using the college transport, parents are also feel complete peace of mind. Finally this study analyzed the transport resources where the students are highly satisfied with bus facilities in our college, where else the suggestion has given as to improve accessibility and service of the transportation facilities.

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